
BIOACOUSTICS AND THE BIOPHYSICS OF HEARING ORGANS

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KEYWORDS

Acoustics, hearing, biophysics, sound waves, audiometry, cochlear implantation, ultrasound diagnostics, auditory system, bioelectric signals, hearing disorders, medical technologies

ABSTRACT

Acoustics is the study of sound waves and their interaction with various environments. The human auditory system operates through complex mechanical and bioelectric processes. Sound waves are gathered through the outer ear and converted into electrical signals in the inner ear. This article examines the basic principles of acoustics, the anatomy and physiology of the auditory system, and the biophysical processes involved in the conversion of sound energy into electrical signals. The use of hearing technologies, such as audiometry, cochlear implantation, and ultrasound diagnostics, is widespread in medicine. The future development of acoustics continues to open new possibilities in medical technology.

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BIOAKUSTIKA VA ESHITTISH ORGANLARINING BIOFIZIKASI

KALIT SO'ZLAR/ КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА:

Akustika, eshitish, biofizika, tovush to'lqinlari, audiometriya, ko'xlear implantatsiya, ultratovush diagnostikasi, eshitish tizimi, bioelektr signallari, eshitish kasalliklari, tibbiy texnologiyalar

ANNOTATSIYA/ АННОТАЦИЯ

Akustika tovush to'lqinlari va ularning turli muhitlar bilan o'zaro ta'sirini o'rganadi. Insonning eshitish tizimi murakkab mexanik va bioelektrik jarayonlar orqali ishlaydi. Ovoz to'lqinlari tashqi quloq orqali to'planadi va ichki quloqda elektr signallariga aylanadi. Ushbu maqolada akustikaning asosiy tamoyillari, eshitish tizimining anatomiyasi va fiziologiyasi, tovush energiyasini elektr signallariga aylantirish bilan bog'liq biofizik jarayonlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Tibbiyotda audiometriya, ko'xlear implantatsiya, ultratovush diagnostikasi kabi eshitish texnologiyalaridan foydalanish keng tarqalgan. Akustikaning kelajakdagi rivojlanishi tibbiy texnologiyada yangi imkoniyatlar ochishda davom etmoqda.

Introduction

Acoustics is the science of the physical properties of sound waves, their propagation, and interaction. Knowledge in this field plays a critical role in medicine, especially in understanding the human auditory system and creating technologies to restore hearing ability. This article covers the basic principles of acoustics, the anatomy and physiology of the auditory system, and the biophysical aspects related to medical applications.

Main body

Acoustics is based on the fundamental physical properties of sound waves. Sound is energy that propagates in the form of vibrations through an elastic medium. The primary parameters of sound are frequency, amplitude, and speed. Frequency (measured in hertz, Hz) represents the number of vibrations per second. The human hearing range spans from 20 Hz to 20,000 Hz. Low-frequency sounds are perceived as bass, while high-frequency sounds are heard as sharper tones. Amplitude measures the intensity of sound, expressed in decibels (dB), with 0 dB being the threshold of hearing and 140 dB representing a painful sound level. Sound speed depends on the physical properties of the medium, with sound traveling at approximately 343 m/s in air and 1,480 m/s in water. These properties are widely used in medical diagnostics, such as ultrasound.

The human auditory system consists of three main parts: the outer ear, middle ear, and inner ear. The outer ear (auricle) collects sound waves and directs them through the external auditory canal to the eardrum. The eardrum vibrates in response to sound waves, and these vibrations are transmitted to the inner ear via the ossicles: malleus, incus, and stapes. In the inner ear, the cochlea, which has a spiral shape, contains the basilar membrane. This membrane is sensitive to sound waves of different frequencies: high-frequency sounds are detected near the base, while low-frequency sounds are detected at the apex. The mechanical vibrations of the basilar membrane are converted into electrical signals by the Organ of Corti, which are then transmitted to the brain via the vestibulocochlear nerve. This process allows the brain to perceive and interpret sound.

The principles of acoustics are widely applied in medicine. Audiometry is used to assess hearing ability by testing responses to sound at various frequencies, which is crucial for identifying patients suitable for cochlear implants or hearing aids. Cochlear implantation is an innovative method that restores hearing by electrically stimulating damaged parts of the inner ear. The technology involves electrodes placed in the cochlea, which convert sound signals into electrical impulses, stimulating the nerves. This allows patients to regain hearing.

The biophysics of the auditory system is crucial in understanding its functioning. Sound vibrations cause mechanical movement in the eardrum, which is transmitted to the inner ear via the ossicles. The movement of the fluid in the cochlea stimulates the basilar membrane, which in turn activates the Organ of Corti. These processes involve electrometric and bioelectric transformations.

The auditory system undergoes complex energetic changes, where sound energy is converted into mechanical energy and then into electrical signals. The system is designed to minimize energy loss during these transformations.

Recent advancements in acoustics have led to numerous innovations in medical technologies. Modern hearing aids can reduce background noise and enhance sound clarity. They can be adjusted to suit individual user needs.

Biomechanical analysis, a new branch of acoustics, studies the mechanical stress generated in tissues due to sound exposure. This research is crucial for improving surgical instruments and developing new treatment methods.

Every year in Uzbekistan, more than 700-800 children are born with congenital hearing loss and deafness, and more than a thousand people are diagnosed with acquired deafness. As of 07.06.2021, more than 1,000 operations on children using cochlear implants have been performed in Uzbekistan. On November 8-9, 2022, an international scientific and reporting conference on the topic "Cochlear Implantation and Postoperative Rehabilitation" was held at the Tashkent Medical Academy and VIVO Clinic in collaboration with the Cochlear company.

A methodological seminar with international participation on the topic "Psychological and pedagogical support of children with cochlear implants" was held in Tashkent and Samarkand.

The main purpose of the seminar was to discuss the results achieved in recent years on the problem of children with hearing impairments. The main goals of this event were to increase the effectiveness of research, exchange experiences and, of course, introduce new deaf-pedagogical developments to increase the effectiveness of rehabilitation of children with hearing impairments.

For example, in 2016, only 150 children with sensorineural deafness or hearing loss were operated on with cochlear implants, while in 2018 this figure was 239, in 2019 it was

320, in 2020 it was 225, and in 2023 250 children were successfully implanted.

Conclusion

The application of acoustics and the biophysics of the auditory system in medicine is vital for restoring hearing abilities and developing new technologies. The human auditory system is the result of complex biological and physical processes, which provide essential knowledge for enhancing the effectiveness of treatments and developing new technologies. The ongoing advancements in acoustics play a pivotal role in creating new medical opportunities and introducing innovative technologies.

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